

HIGH-ALTITUDE MICROALGAE AS NOVEL BIOFACTORIES: ADAPTATION STRATEGIES, USES, AND BARRIERS TO APPLICATION IN ECUADOR

Carla SANDOVAL-GUANO¹, Santiago ZÁRATE-BACA¹, Andrea CHILQUINGA¹, Sania ORTEGA-ANDRADE¹, Vincenzo LONGO²

¹eCIER Research Group, Department of Biotechnology, Universidad Técnica del Norte, Av. 17 de Julio 5–21 y Gral. José María Córdova, Ibarra 100150, Ecuador

²Institute of Biology and Agricultural Biotechnology, National Research Council, Pisa, Italy

email: casandoval@utn.edu.ec

Keywords: *Andean high-altitude microalgae, Lakes, Lagoons, Blue Biotechnology, Photobioreactor, Bioeconomy, Biodiversity.*

Abstract

Andean High-altitude microalgae represent a distinct extremophilic biodiversity shaped by intense UV radiation, low nutrient availability, and marked temperature fluctuations. These environmental pressures have generated phylogenetically diverse communities with exceptional physiological resilience, particularly among genera such as *Chlamydomonas*, *Scenedesmus*, *Chlorella*, and *Synedra*. Their ecological adaptations make them strong candidates for biotechnological development. High-altitude species synthesize metabolites with important industrial value, including UV-protective mycosporine-like amino acids, bioactive polysaccharides with cryoprotective and immunomodulatory functions, and high-value pigments such as lutein and astaxanthin. Many also accumulate stress-induced lipids suitable for biofuel production, underscoring their metabolic versatility under fluctuating conditions. Efforts to cultivate these microalgae increasingly rely on specialized photobioreactors, extremophile-optimized media, and adaptive laboratory evolution to enhance productivity and metabolite yield. Resulting applications are focused on cosmetics, nutraceuticals, bioremediation agents, sustainable pigments, and renewable energy feedstocks, turning these species into noble candidates for further industrial applications. However, substantial research gaps remain. Genomic and metabolomic resources are limited, constraining pathway engineering and strain improvement. Standardized cultivation methodologies are still lacking, and ecological datasets necessary to link environmental drivers with metabolic expression remain incomplete. Future work integrating multi-omics and scalability of the cultivation and harvesting processes will be essential to fully exploit the biotechnological potential of Andean high-altitude microalgae while supporting conservation of their native habitats.

Received: 10 Oct. 2025, Revised: 10 Nov. 2025, Accepted: 10 Nov. 2025, Published: 16 December 2025

SANDOVAL-GUANO, C., ZÁRATE-BACA, S., Choloquinga, A., ORTEGA-ANDRADE, S., & Longo, V. (2025). HIGH-ALTITUDE MICROALGAE AS NOVEL BIOFACTORIES: ADAPTATION STRATEGIES, USES, AND BARRIERS TO APPLICATION IN ECUADOR. *Pescuitul Și Acvacultura (Fishing and Aquaculture)*, 2(4), 38–54. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18031362>

Introduction

The province of Imbabura, known as the "Province of Lakes," is part of a landscape of lacustrine ecosystems ideal for the development of microalgae bioprospecting [1]. Within its small geographical area are the Yahuarcocha, Piñan, Mojanda, Puruhanta, and Cuicocha lagoons, as well as Lake San Pablo [2]. The latter is one of the main tourist attractions of the Otavalo canton and of limnological scientific interest, as researchers seek to understand its behavior and biodiversity [3].

Limnological research [4] indicates that Lake San Pablo is a mesotrophic lake undergoing eutrophication due to climate change and human activities. Ecosystem degradation leads to biodiversity loss, forcing researchers to race against time to prevent the extinction of vulnerable species [5].

Global markets for bioprospecting generate significant economic returns through the accumulation of knowledge from strain isolation, maintenance, and conservation in laboratories [6]. Isolated strains must meet several requirements, such as ease of handling, resistance, and easy growth [7]. This facilitates the identification of strains suitable for molecular, biochemical, physicochemical, and genetic manipulation for production purposes [8].

The natural resources of Ecuadorian territory are of paramount importance to biotechnology, as the environmental, geographical, and topographical conditions generate a wealth of genetic material suitable for bioprospecting [9]. The province of Imbabura, with its ecosystems, could be considered a strategic area for bioprospecting to analyze microalgal biodiversity with biotechnological potential [10].

High-Altitude Microalgae - Diversity and Ecology

Ecuador is considered one of the 17 megadiverse countries in the world due to its biodiversity. This is mainly due to geographical location, presence of the Andes mountain range, the influence of the Pacific Ocean, Humboldt marine currents, and the El Niño phenomenon that model terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, in addition to 91 continental ecosystems and 21 marine ecosystems. In particular, the inter-Andean region of the country has been privileged with imposing volcanoes, mountains, lakes, and high Andean lagoons [11]. The country's geography has given rise to the formation of lakes due to various geological and glacial processes, especially of volcanic origin, located over 3000 m.a.l.s. [12]. Therefore, there are significant differences in environmental, physicochemical, and ecological conditions [13]. This is how they become ideal habitats for extremophile organisms since they are exposed to high UV radiation, intense sunlight, extreme daily fluctuations, strong winds, low atmospheric pressure, oligotrophy, among others, influencing morphology, resilient physiology, and the production of unique metabolites of industrial interest [14], [15], [16]. Microalgae and cyanobacteria are photosynthetic single-celled microorganisms that capture a considerable amount of atmospheric CO₂ and release O₂ in aquatic environments [17]. In addition to water, CO₂, and biogenic compounds such as nitrogen and phosphorus, they offer higher biomass yields than terrestrial plants [18]. These resources comprise approximately 72,500 identified species, although it is estimated that there are close to 1 million species worldwide [19]. The predominant groups are eukaryotes and diatoms found here (*Bacillariophyceae*), golden algae (*Charophyceae*), and green algae (*Chlorophyceae*). The

group of prokaryotic species known as cyanobacteria (*Cyanophyceae*), together with green algae and Diatoms, is considered the most important in biotechnological applications [20].

In Ecuador, more than 1500 species of microalgae have been identified in different aquatic ecosystems, of which 106 are present in lake ecosystems at 3500 m.a.s.l [14]. This information has been acquired to have an overview of the distribution and diversity of ecosystems [9]. However, despite ecological importance, knowledge about microalgae biodiversity and ecology remains limited. It is known that these organisms have specific requirements for reproduction and growth, so the presence or absence of a particular species can modify water quality [3], [21], [22], [23]. Therefore, understanding the composition and dynamics of micro-algal communities is essential for freshwater ecosystems. Environmental parameters in high-altitude areas are directly related to photosynthetic microorganisms' nutrient availability and diversity in water bodies [2], [24]. Therefore, environmental conditions in Ecuador favor the survival of microalgae and the increase in the concentration of antioxidant molecules of biotechnological interest, as they are exposed to extreme conditions [25], [26].

Different taxonomic groups exhibit specific adaptations to water bodies' physicochemical parameters, as this condition is vital in high-altitude ecosystems [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]. Altitude acts as a stable geographic determinant that dictates broad climate gradients like UV radiation tolerance. *Chlorella* and *Scenedesmus* high-altitude microalgae develop protective mechanisms, such as high levels of carotenoid and polyphenol accumulation, to mitigate the damage caused by UV radiation [32], [33]. On the other hand, temperature generally decreases with increasing altitude, which results in the selection of cold-adapted (psychrophilic) species that can maintain their metabolic activity in lower temperature ranges. Finally, atmospheric pressure decreases with increasing altitude, favoring certain species, such as cyanobacteria, which are provided with gas vesicles to regulate buoyancy in response to changes in pressure [32], [34]. Therefore, communities of these organisms can change qualitatively and quantitatively depending on the water's physical and chemical conditions. [35]. For example, the phylum Bacillariophyta population declines significantly due to competition because of its weak adaptation mechanism to high radiation levels [31]. Furthermore, the Cyanobacteria phylum is characterized by independent growth under environmental conditions and can be dominant in different ecosystems [36]. In contrast, the Chlorophyta phylum is abundant and diverse in freshwater bodies because it has both autotrophic and heterotrophic adaptation mechanisms; its abundance and distribution determine water quality [23], [27].

In eight lakes spanning different altitudes in the Ecuadorian Tropical Andes identified a total of 92 microalgae genera encompassing Bacillariophyta, Chlorophyta, Glaucophyta, Coprophyte, Cyanophyta, and Euglenophyta. Despite limitations in taxonomic identification, this study managed to reveal a positive association between Bacillariophyta, Euglenophyta, Charophyta, and temperature, suggesting that the microalgae taxa could be more affected by temperature changes. However, global warming is changing ecosystem dynamics and, with it, the way physicochemical factors interact. In addition, due to anthropogenic activities, increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations are causing further alterations in the oceans and in the freshwater pH, threatening ecosystem diversity and functionality [23]. The situation is probably more critical in this type of high-altitude ecosystem, and research is still incipient in understanding the synergistic factors affecting Andean species.

General Overview of the Microalgae Metabolites with Biotechnological Relevance

Microalgae are considered natural biofactories that transform organic substrates and carbon dioxide into valuable primary and secondary metabolites (Table 1). These compounds are helpful in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and aquaculture industries.

Table 1. Overview of metabolites derived from microalgae and their bioactive potential.

Molecule	Microalgae	Reported bioactivity	Reference
Polyunsaturated-fatty acids (PUFAs)	<i>Nannochloropsis</i> <i>Schizochytrium</i>	Nutraceuticals Functional supplements Biofuels	[37], [38]
Pigments/ Carotenoids (β-carotene, astaxanthin, lutein)	<i>Dunaliella salina</i> <i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	Photoprotectors Antioxidants	[39], [40]
Protein pigments Phycocyanins (Phycobiliproteins)	<i>Spirulina</i>	Natural pigments Antioxidants	[41], [42]
Carbohydrates Polysaccharides Exopolysaccharides	<i>Porphyridium</i> <i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	Nutraceuticals Pharmaceuticals Gelling agents Ecological roles	[43]
Bioactive proteins and peptides	<i>Chlorella</i> <i>Spirulina</i>	Functional supplements Antioxidants	[44]
Micronutrients Vitamins (A, B12, E)	<i>Chlorella</i> <i>Spirulina</i>	Pharmaceuticals	[44]
Secondary metabolites Phytosterols and phenolic compounds	<i>Nannochloropsis</i>	Nutraceuticals Antioxidants	[45]
Poly-hydroxy-alkanoates (PHA)	<i>Synechocystis</i>	Biodegradable plastics	[46]

Their versatility in adapting to diverse environments for growth, including wastewater and aquatic substrates with high nutrients or pollutant loads, makes them a sustainable alternative for generating metabolite-rich biomass and promoting the production of high-value-added compounds such as pigments, lipids, carbohydrates, and proteins [47], [48].

Microalgae polysaccharides

Exopolysaccharides (EPS) derived from microalgae are essential extracellular compounds for the resilience of these organisms. High molecular weight sulfated EPS, neutral and acids EPS, and uronic acids produced by *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Chlorella vulgaris*,

Neochloris oleoabundans, *Dunaliella salina*, and other sea microalgae, participate in the capture, recycling, and immobilization of large quantities of carbon dioxide through the formation of biofilms, cell aggregations, biomass fixation, stabilization of other beneficial microbial aquatic communities, and sedimentation [49], [50], [51]. This dynamic contributes to regulating the global climate and to sustaining the trophic relationships of marine biodiversity [5], [52].

Microalgae-derived exopolysaccharides also create an external protective matrix that protects and facilitates adaptation to extreme conditions, such as UV radiation, desiccation, and changes in environmental salinity [53], [54]. Finally, the particles' aggregation contributes to particulate organic matter as food for filter-feeding organisms, heterotrophic bacteria, zooplankton, and protozoa, thereby promoting energy transfer within the food web [5].

In another context, the bioactivity of EPS includes the protective effect against oxidative stress, an attractive feature in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries [55]. In healthcare, some sulfated EPS have demonstrated antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and antitumoral effects [56].

Microalgae pigments

The microalgae synthesize different pigments that allow them to capture sunlight to perform their photosynthetic function. Microalgae pigments are grouped into chlorophylls, carotenoids, and phycobilins. The impact of sunlight is an important stress factor that promotes pigment production, particularly in some high-altitude microalgae species [57].

Some notable examples include β -carotene (*Dunaliella salina*), which has shown antioxidant activity via a free radical-neutralization mechanism. The phycocyanins (*Spirulina*) and phycobiliproteins play roles in protecting against UV radiation and reducing specific inflammatory processes [30], [58]. For their part, astaxanthin and lutein (*Haematococcus astaxanthin*) have demonstrated inhibitory effects on the proliferation of some cancer cell lines [59], [60].

Microalgae polyunsaturated fatty acids

The microalgae are a sustainable source of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), especially omega-3 fatty acids such as eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) (*Nannochloropsis* and *Phaeodactylum tricornerutum*) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) (*Shizochytrium* and *Cryptocodinium cohnii*), and omega-6 fatty acids such as arachidonic acid (ARA) [61]. The PUFAs are essential molecules for human health and exhibit bioactivities as cardioprotectors, reducing triglyceride levels and improving endothelial function [62]. DHA is essential for brain development and cognitive function. EPA and ARA modulate eicosanoid synthesis during the inflammatory process [63], [64]. Finally, some PUFAs act indirectly to regulate antioxidant gene expression, serving as a protective mechanism against oxidative stress.

Microalgae polyphenols

The polyphenols are secondary metabolites characterized by their colors across the red-to-blue spectrum. The biological activity of these molecules in microalgae is to protect against UV damage and prevent oxidative degradation. Their biological relevance makes them potential antioxidants, anti-inflammatories, neuroprotectors, and antimicrobial metabolites [65]. In particular, quercetin and gallic acid inhibit inflammatory mediators and exhibit antibacterial activity [66].

Cultivation and Biotechnological Applications

Andean freshwater microalgae from high-altitude lakes, lagoons, and water bodies grow at specific environmental conditions determined by the Andean mountains and their surroundings. In fact, specific conditions of pH, temperature, oxygen and carbon dioxide, UV radiation, and nutrient supply exert distinct effects on microalgae survival and metabolic behavior. For cultivation purposes, the environmental parameters for high-altitude microalgae production at the lab scale are depicted in Table 2. Among all parameters, temperature is the most significant because these species can grow at lower temperatures than other cell factories, so cooling costs can be reduced [16], [67], [68].

Table 2. Environmental cultivation parameters for high altitude microalgae species.

Parameter	Common <i>in-situ</i> range in high-alt/Andean lakes	Common lab cultivation range for high-alt isolates
pH	6.5 – 8.5	Most cold-adapted strains grow well in neutral to slightly alkaline media
Temperature (water/culture)	0 – 15 °C Some tropical high-alt lakes show ~7 – 22°C depending on season/depth.	Psychrophilic strains show optimum ≤15 °C; others are psychrotolerant and grow to ~20 °C. Standard mesophiles are often kept at 20–25 °C, but Andean strains frequently prefer lower temperatures.
Dissolved oxygen (DO)	High variability — often 8–12 mg·L ⁻¹	Maintain ≥5 mg·L ⁻¹ in cultures for healthy photoautotrophic growth; aeration/agitation used to avoid oxygen depletion in dense cultures.
Dissolved CO₂ / DIC	High-alt waters can be low in dissolved CO ₂ but receive strong photoperiodic CO ₂ drawdown	CO ₂ supply or bicarbonate supplementation is often used in cultivation to avoid carbon limitation. Maintain pH with CO ₂ sparging when running continuous cultures (target depends on species, often pH ~7.5 – 8.0).
Salinity/conductivity	0.02–0.03 mS·cm ⁻¹ Some high-alt lakes are mineralized or saline depending on soil geology	Freshwater strains: near 0–1 PSU (practically 0–0.5 g·L ⁻¹ salts). Halotolerant freshwater Andean isolates are scarce.
Nitrogen (bulk: NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺)	<1 mg·L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	Culture practice: standard freshwater media (BG-11, BBM) supply 50–100+ mg·L ⁻¹ N (varies by recipe). For nitrogen-fixing cyanobacteria, use N-free or low-N media to promote heterocyst formation and N ₂ fixation (e.g., BG-11).
Phosphorus (PO₄³⁻ / SRP)	<0.1 mg·L ⁻¹	Cultures: media phosphate concentrations are typically in the 0.1–1.0 mg·L ⁻¹ (or higher) range depending on recipe. Limiting P can be used experimentally to induce lipid accumulation or other stress responses.

Biotechnological Applications

Microalgae cultivation supports a wide range of biotechnological applications, offering sustainable solutions across nutraceuticals, cosmetics, agriculture, environment, and sustainable bioenergy. Andean high-altitude freshwater microalgae, especially *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, and *Chlamydomonas* species (Table 3), are considered cell factories not only for producing versatile compounds such as antioxidants and biofertilizers, but also for enhancing biochemical processes for carbon sequestration, water quality, and sustainable bioenergy. Their adaptability and biochemical diversity underpin their growing biotechnological value.

Table 3. Main Andean high-altitude freshwater microalgae and their biotechnological uses.

Species/Genus	Biotechnological applications	Reference
<i>Ankistrodesmus falcatus</i>	Bioenergy, water quality	[69]
<i>Asterarcys quadricellulare</i>	Nutrition, pharmaceuticals	[69], [70]
<i>Chlorella spp.</i>	Antioxidants, biofertilizers, carbon capture, biofuel	[57], [69], [71], [72], [73]
<i>Chlamydomonas spp.</i>	Antioxidants, pollutant removal, bioenergy	[57], [70]
<i>Scenedesmus spp.</i>	Bioenergy, water quality, agriculture, antioxidants	[57], [69], [70], [72]
<i>Synedra, Cosmarium</i>	Water quality indicators in high-altitude lakes	[16]

Nutraceuticals and Cosmetics: Antioxidant and Photoprotective Compounds

The diversity of freshwater habitats at different altitudes leads to variation in pigment composition and antioxidant profiles, enhancing their functional potential. Species like *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, and *Chlamydomonas* are rich in polyphenols, carotenoids, vitamins, and other bioactive molecules with potent antioxidant and photoprotective properties, making them valuable for nutraceutical and cosmetic products [57], [71], [74], [75]. These compounds exhibit anti-inflammatory, anti-UV, and anti-aging effects, supporting their use in functional foods and skincare, positioning microalgae as eco-friendly alternatives to synthetic cosmetics [71], [74], [75].

Agriculture: Biofertilizers and Biostimulants for Cold-Climate Crops

Microalgae such as *Chlorella* and *Scenedesmus* are used as biofertilizers and biostimulants, enhancing nutrient uptake, plant growth, and stress tolerance in crops, including those in cold climates [72], [73], [76], [77]. Their extracts contribute biofertilizing and biostimulant effects by producing phytohormones, amino acids, and micronutrients that promote root development and resilience to abiotic stress [73], [77].

Environmental Biotechnology: Carbon Sequestration and Water Quality Enhancement

Microalgae act as efficient carbon sinks, capturing CO₂ while simultaneously treating wastewater by removing nitrogen, phosphorus, and heavy metals. In fact, high-altitude microalgae demonstrate efficient carbon dioxide sequestration, with species like *Chlorella* and *Scenedesmus* are adapted to strong sunlight and temperature extremes, exhibit enhanced photosynthetic efficiency capable of removing significant amounts of CO₂ and nutrients from water, improving water quality, and supporting climate mitigation [69], [78], [79], [80]. These

microalgae are also used as bioindicators for monitoring and sustaining water quality in sensitive ecosystems [16], [81].

Bioenergy: Feasibility and Sustainability

Freshwater microalgae, especially *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, and *Ankistrodesmus*, are promising feedstocks for biofuel production due to their high growth rates and lipid content [69], [78], [82]. Cultivation on marginal or high-altitude lands is feasible and can be integrated with wastewater treatment for cost-effective, sustainable bioenergy production [78], [82]. Challenges remain in scaling production and optimizing energy efficiency, particularly for cultivation in cold or high-altitude environments, but hybrid systems (wastewater-fed photobioreactors) show promise for integrated bioenergy production [83].

Improving cultivation scalability while preserving native biodiversity

Several considerations should be taken into account to improve scalability, thereby preserving native biodiversity and integrating diverse crop practices within the communities surrounding the lakes. Additionally, it is crucial to integrate microalgae cultures into agroecological practices, thereby minimizing chemical inputs and preserving natural habitats.

Microalgae can be cultivated using farm waste and integrated into closed-loop systems, thereby reducing the need for external inputs. Due to the characteristics of microalgae, it can be used in wastewater treatment for a dual purpose: cleaning water for irrigation runoff, treating livestock effluents, and producing biomass, which can be used as a mix of algal biomass with compost to accelerate decomposition and nutrient release [84], [85].

Taking all these aspects into account, the most feasible approach for microalgae production is to consider local, community-based scenarios where production focuses on local use and improves the condition of the crops of interest to determine a geographic location, specific geographic parameters, such as latitude, longitude, altitude, the presence of slopes, and water sources, must be considered. Subsequently, it is necessary to include environmental parameters such as temperature, UV radiation, annual precipitation, relative humidity, and day length, which vary according to the season [86], [87].

Large-scale production depends on climatic conditions, light incidence in each area, reactor design, and operating conditions. Therefore, the productivity obtained in different geographic zones cannot be extrapolated [88]. Thus, the development of theoretical scenarios is required to simulate the possible behavior of microorganisms in different production system configurations, which can be open (pond-type) or closed (tubular photobioreactors or panels). However, scenario design can present bottlenecks due to the large amount of information required for large-scale production, which can include preliminary experimental trials, the effects of new conditions, and the uncertainty of microorganisms' responses to operating conditions [89].

For large-scale microalgae production, two types of designs could be established in Ecuador framework, depending on the ambient light and temperature specific to each production area [88]. One design uses open systems, in which cultures are exposed to environmental conditions, and their construction and operation are relatively easy. The other design uses closed systems called photobioreactors (PBRs), which can be totally or partially isolated from environmental conditions, making their construction more difficult and costly [89]. Selecting the reactor shape requires considering the species to be cultivated, its stress resistance, and its nutritional and light requirements [90].

The design of each culture system must ensure high volumetric productivity, ease of operation, and low investment and maintenance costs. The main factors determining the reliability of production systems are the capture and distribution of sunlight, nutrient mixing, and gas control systems (CO₂ and O₂). Additionally, scalability and long-term material durability must be considered. Therefore, numerous designs have been proposed that combine the benefits of both open and closed systems [91].

The most commonly used systems for large-scale microalgae production are open pond-type systems and closed systems, such as vertical and horizontal panels and tubes [88]. The main factors highlighted in these designs are production costs and the feasibility of controlling physicochemical parameters for the growth of the microorganisms of interest. One of the differences identified is that horizontal tubular fiber-retaining bromeliads (FRBs) capture and distribute more light within the system, favoring microalgae growth compared to panel or pond-type systems [92]

Ethical and conservation aspects of Andean microalgae bioprospecting

The Constitution of Ecuador incorporates the principle of Good Living (Sumak Kawsay), inspired by Indigenous worldviews, which promotes harmony between people and the natural environment. This ethical approach recognizes that biodiversity is not only an economic resource but a common heritage that must be protected to guarantee the lives of present and future generations. Socially, the Constitution fosters citizen participation in environmental management and establishes collective responsibility for caring for ecosystems, integrating values such as reciprocity, solidarity, and sustainability. Furthermore, granting inherent rights to nature breaks with the traditional anthropocentric view. It promotes a model of coexistence that places biodiversity conservation at the heart of public policy and social life [93][94].

In addition, high-altitude microalgae are used to link to lakes and lagoons of the Andean region, which are characterized as bodies of water of glacial and volcanic origin, located in high mountain areas, which play a fundamental role as natural water reservoirs and climate regulators, giving them interesting and potential characteristics from a biotechnological application point of view. Furthermore, they harbor a great diversity of flora and fauna adapted to extreme altitude and temperature conditions, making them areas of great ecological and cultural value. However, their balance can be affected by human activities such as intensive agriculture and climate change, highlighting the need to conserve them as vital sources of biodiversity and water in the region

Based on this background, it is necessary to consider that all species isolated from the national territory must have their respective environmental permits and framework agreements, which cover research conducted using these natural resources. Furthermore, the proposed techniques for sampling and sample collection must have the least possible environmental impact and be non-extractive. In this sense, one of the advantages of cultivating microalgae is that an initial sample is required, which, under appropriate conditions, can be adapted to in vitro conditions to obtain a constant biomass without returning to the source. However, the most significant environmental impact of bioprospecting microalgae is the use of diesel-powered motorboats, which could cause oil spills. Also, in the downstream process for microalgae, some toxic reagents are used to isolate molecules with industrial potential. From this point of view, some constraints should be taken into account to apply determined technologies within local areas.

Integration within sustainable, climate-adaptive bioeconomic systems

Within the conditions of Ecuador, fundamental elements that promote this industry at the local level must be considered. Different production scenarios can be designed that consider economic, bioethical, environmental, and social aspects, providing a framework for assessing the feasibility of microalgae production in Ecuador. To integrate microalgae cultivation into a bioeconomy system, it is necessary to consider Ecuador's legal framework, as well as resources that can guide the application of this bioprocess for sustainable microalgae production. The general regulations are described below.

Figure 1. Ecuador's legal framework for improving microalgae cultivation

The organic Law of Aquaculture and Fisheries establishes a legal framework for the protection, conservation, and sustainable use of aquatic ecosystems and hydrobiological resources, covering all phases of aquaculture and fisheries, reproduction, cultivation, processing, storage, distribution, and commercialization. The law explicitly allows for the cultivation of aquatic species, including microalgae, which are recognized as an essential input for aquaculture (e.g., as feed for fish, shrimp, and mollusks). The use of alternative feed in aquaculture systems could be an ecosystem-based approach to ensure sustainability and food security [95]. Microalgae as a feed source could improve aquaculture in Ecuador. In fact, there is an essential institute in the coastal region, CENAIM (Centro Nacional de Acuicultura e Investigaciones Marinas), linked to ESPOL (The Escuela Superior Politécnica del Litoral), which is leading research on the application of microalgae in aquaculture. By regulating aquaculture inputs, the law supports Ecuador's goal of producing healthy, sustainable food.

The principles through Ecuador's Organic Code of the Environment (Código Orgánico del Ambiente, COA) directly support sustainable production systems, including the cultivation

of microalgae and microorganisms, by requiring environmental permits, impact assessments, and compliance with sustainability standards.

The inclusive circular economy is one of the first circular economy laws in Latin America, connecting the economy with social inclusion, thereby promoting the participation of vulnerable groups in decision-making and the growth of potential sources of income in local markets. In the context of microalgae production, this emerging industry transforms waste streams into valuable products (biofuels, bioplastics, fertilizers, proteins), aligning perfectly with LOECI's principles of resource efficiency, waste valorization, and social inclusion.

Finally, the microalgae industry is relatively new and has a minimal baseline of knowledge. Still, there is the support of a guiding document such as White Book on the Circular Economy in Ecuador, which introduces principles of sustainability, innovation, and use of waste that are directly connected with the bioprospecting of microalgae; in fact, it places the diversity of Ecuador as an engine of development to change the productive matrix of Ecuador and leave the dependence on fossil fuels [96].

References

- [1] Z. A. Mendoza, "UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LOJA ÁREA AGROPECUARIA Y DE RECURSOS NATURALES RENOVABLES CARRERA DE INGENIERIA FORESTAL GUIA DE METODOS PARA MEDIR LA BIODIVERSIDAD."
- [2] G. Gunkel, "Limnology of an equatorial high mountain lake in Ecuador, Lago San Pablo," *Limnologica*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 113–120, May 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0075-9511(00)80005-5.
- [3] J. E. Casallas and G. Gunkel, "Algunos aspectos limnológicos de un lago altoandino: el lago San Pablo, Ecuador."
- [4] C. Miño and J. Rodríguez, *EVALUACIÓN DEL ESTADO TRÓFICO EN RELACIÓN AL COMPORTAMIENTO DE LOS PARÁMETROS FÍSICOS Y BIOLÓGICOS DEL LAGO SAN PABLO, ECUADOR*, vol. 1, no. SEPTIEMBRE. 2018.
- [5] L. M. Gómez Luna, "MICROALGAS: ASPECTOS ECOLÓGICOS Y BIOTECNOLÓGICOS," 2007.
- [6] G. O. Fistarol *et al.*, "Rapid isolation of culturable microalgae from a tropical shallow lake system," *J Appl Phycol*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 1807–1819, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s10811-018-1404-7.
- [7] R. J. P. Barten, R. H. Wijffels, and M. J. Barbosa, "Bioprospecting and characterization of temperature tolerant microalgae from Bonaire," *Algal Res*, vol. 50, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.algal.2020.102008.
- [8] M. Cuaresma, M. Janssen, C. V?lchez, and R. H. Wijffels, "Horizontal or vertical photobioreactors? How to improve microalgae photosynthetic efficiency," *Bioresour Technol*, vol. 102, no. 8, pp. 5129–5137, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2011.01.078.
- [9] J. O. Tirado *et al.*, "Molecular characterization and antioxidant potential of Andean chlorophytes from Ecuador," *J Appl Pharm Sci*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 56–60, 2017, doi: 10.7324/JAPS.2017.70510.
- [10] C. Guamán and P. González, "Catálogo De Microalgas Y Cianobacterias," 2016, [Online]. Available: <http://energia.org.ec/cic/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Catlogo-de-Microalgas-y-Cianobacterias-del-Ecuador.pdf>
- [11] S., O. P., & V. G. Báez, "Una breve historia del espacio ecuatoriano. Fraga Impresores. ," Ecuador , 2004.
- [12] IGEPN, "Home - Instituto Geofísico - EPN. <http://www.igepn.edu.ec/> ."

- [13] Z. Arce, A. Arias, and A. Mera, "Organismos extremófilos en el ojo de la ciencia," *Revista Médica Herediana*, vol. 28, no. 1, p. 70, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.20453/rmh.v28i1.3079.
- [14] M. C. Guamán-Burneo, N. González-Romero, A. Santillán-Sarmiento, M. C. Guamán-Burneo, N. González-Romero, and A. Santillán-Sarmiento, "Microalgal Diversity in the Ecuadorian Tropical Andes and Its Association with Abiotic Factors," *Hydrobiology 2025, Vol. 4*, vol. 4, no. 4, p. 28, Oct. 2025, doi: 10.3390/HYDROBIOLOGY4040028.
- [15] T. Huaranca Reyes, C. Chiellini, E. Barozzi, C. Sandoval, C. Echeverría, and L. Guglielminetti, "Exploring the Physiological Multiplicity of Native Microalgae from the Ecuadorian Highland, Italian Lowland and Indoor Locations in Response to UV-B," *Int J Mol Sci*, vol. 24, no. 2, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3390/ijms24021346.
- [16] E. Delgado-Fernández, D. Cruz, R. Ayavaca, Á. Benítez, and B. Hernández, "Microalgal Diversity as Bioindicators for Assessing and Sustaining Water Quality in the High Mountain Lakes of Quimsacocha, Azuay, Ecuador," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 17, no. 4, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.3390/SU17041620/S1.
- [17] J.-B. Beigbeder and J.-M. Lavoie, "Effect of photoperiods and CO₂ concentrations on the cultivation of carbohydrate-rich *P. kessleri* microalgae for the sustainable production of bioethanol," *Journal of CO₂ Utilization*, vol. 58, p. 101934, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jcou.2022.101934.
- [18] K. Szwarc, D. Szwarc, and M. Zieliński, "Removal of biogenic compounds from the post-fermentation effluent in a culture of *Chlorella vulgaris*," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 111–117, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11356-019-05162-6.
- [19] V. Ebenezer, L. K. Medlin, and J.-S. Ki, "Molecular Detection, Quantification, and Diversity Evaluation of Microalgae," *Marine Biotechnology*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 129–142, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1007/s10126-011-9427-y.
- [20] E. Jacob-Lopes, C. H. G. Scoparo, L. M. C. F. Lacerda, and T. T. Franco, "Effect of light cycles (night/day) on CO₂ fixation and biomass production by microalgae in photobioreactors," *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 306–310, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.cep.2008.04.007.
- [21] A. Vélez-Azañero, S. Lozano, and K. Cáceres-Torres, "DIVERSIDAD DE FITOPLANCTON COMO INDICADOR DE CALIDAD DE AGUA EN LA CUENCA BAJA DEL RÍO LURÍN, LIMA, PERÚ," *Ecología Aplicada*, vol. 15, no. 2, p. 69, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.21704/rea.v15i2.745.
- [22] F. Caicedo, "'OCEANS AND LAKES' INTERUNIVERSITY MASTER OF SCIENCE IN MARINE AND LACUSTRINE SCIENCE AND MANAGEMENT THE STRUCTURING ROLE OF THREE DIFFERENT TYPES OF MACROPHYTES ON THE PLANKTONIC COMMUNITIES OF LAKE SAN PABLO, A TROPICAL ANDEAN SYSTEM IN NORTHERN ECUADOR," 2019.
- [23] G. N. Guamán-Burneo MC, *Catálogo de microalgas y cianobacterias de agua dulce del Ecuador*. 2016.
- [24] D. Gökçe, "Algae as an indicator of water quality," *Algae-Organisms for Imminent Biotechnology*, 2016.
- [25] M. Costa, J. Costa-Rodrigues, M. H. Fernandes, P. Barros, V. Vasconcelos, and R. Martins, "Marine Cyanobacteria Compounds with Anticancer Properties: A Review on the Implication of Apoptosis," *Mar Drugs*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 2181–2207, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.3390/md10102181.
- [26] M. Cevallos-Rivera *et al.*, "Exploring freshwater microalgae diversity in Yahuarcocha and San Pablo highland lakes for biotechnological applications in the Ecuadorian Andean," *Heliyon*, vol. 11, no. 13, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2025.e43064.
- [27] E. G. Bellinger and D. C. Sigeo, *Freshwater Algae: Identification and Use as Bioindicators*. John Wiley and Sons, 2010. doi: 10.1002/9780470689554.
- [28] M., B. S., & P. S. Devlin, "Comparison of five methods for assessing impacts of nutrient enrichment using estuarine case studies," *Biogeochemistry*, 106(2), 177-205, 2011.

- [29] S. Li, X. Li, and S. H. Ho, "Microalgae as a solution of third world energy crisis for biofuels production from wastewater toward carbon neutrality: An updated review," *Chemosphere*, vol. 291, p. 132863, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2021.132863.
- [30] C. Li, H. Wu, H. Wu, W. Xiang, J. Xu, and T. Li, "Enhancing Phycoerythrin Production of Marine Red Microalga *Porphyridium purpureum* with Low Salinity and Semi-Continuous Culture Strategy," *Mar Drugs*, vol. 23, no. 9, Sep. 2025, doi: 10.3390/md23090361.
- [31] P. Wang, J. Ma, X. Wang, and Q. Tan, "Rising atmospheric CO₂ levels result in an earlier cyanobacterial bloom-maintenance phase with higher algal biomass," *Water Res*, vol. 185, p. 116267, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.WATRES.2020.116267.
- [32] J. Geist, "Integrative freshwater ecology and biodiversity conservation," *Ecol Indic*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 1507–1516, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.1016/J.ECOLIND.2011.04.002.
- [33] W. Wang, Z. He, J. Lv, X. Liu, S. Xie, and J. Feng, "Cyanobacteria as dominant mediator of altitudinal gradient effects on phytoplankton community diversity in freshwater ecosystems: Evidences from the freshwater Lakes along the Hu Line," *Water Res X*, vol. 26, p. 100281, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.1016/J.WROA.2024.100281.
- [34] T. Chen *et al.*, "Manganese Ferrite Nanoparticle-Assisted Enhancement of Photosynthetic Carbon Sequestration in Microalgae," *Sustainability 2025, Vol. 17*, vol. 17, no. 10, May 2025, doi: 10.3390/SU17104303.
- [35] L. de Winter, "Circadian rhythms in microalgae production," 2015, [Online]. Available: <http://edepot.wur.nl/345221>
- [36] S. Cirés and Antonio. Quesada de Corral, *Catálogo de cianobacterias planctónicas potencialmente tóxicas de las aguas continentales españolas*. Ministerio Medio Ambiente y Medio Rural y Marino, 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sergas.es/Saude-publica/Documents/1477/CATÁLOGO CIRES QUESADA.pdf>
- [37] A. Santin, M. T. Russo, M. I. Ferrante, S. Balzano, I. Orefice, and A. Sardo, "Highly Valuable Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids from Microalgae: Strategies to Improve Their Yields and Their Potential Exploitation in Aquaculture," Dec. 01, 2021, *MDPI*. doi: 10.3390/molecules26247697.
- [38] W. Chen, T. Li, S. Du, H. Chen, and Q. Wang, "Microalgal polyunsaturated fatty acids: Hotspots and production techniques," 2023, *Frontiers Media S.A.* doi: 10.3389/fbioe.2023.1146881.
- [39] K. Chekanov, "Diversity and Distribution of Carotenogenic Algae in Europe: A Review," Feb. 01, 2023, *MDPI*. doi: 10.3390/md21020108.
- [40] T. Lafarga, A. Sánchez-Zurano, A. Morillas-España, and F. G. Ación-Fernández, "Extremophile microalgae as feedstock for high-value carotenoids: A review," Oct. 01, 2021, *John Wiley and Sons Inc.* doi: 10.1111/ijfs.15069.
- [41] Z. Yu *et al.*, "Phycocyanin from microalgae: A comprehensive review covering microalgal culture, phycocyanin sources and stability," Jun. 01, 2024, *Elsevier Ltd.* doi: 10.1016/j.foodres.2024.114362.
- [42] X. Wang, Y. Xie, Z. Zhou, R. Ruan, C. Zhou, and Y. Cheng, "Factors Influencing Phycocyanin Synthesis in Microalgae and Culture Strategies: Toward Efficient Production of Alternative Proteins," Jul. 01, 2025, *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)*. doi: 10.3390/su17135962.
- [43] P. Parmar, R. Kumar, Y. Neha, and V. Srivatsan, "Microalgae as next generation plant growth additives: Functions, applications, challenges and circular bioeconomy based solutions," 2023, *Frontiers Media S.A.* doi: 10.3389/fpls.2023.1073546.

- [44] J. Ampofo and Lord Abbey, “Microalgae: Bioactive Composition, Health Benefits, Safety and Prospects as Potential High-Value Ingredients for the Functional Food Industry,” Jun. 01, 2022, *MDPI*. doi: 10.3390/foods11121744.
- [45] L. Zhou, X. Duan, K. Li, D. R. A. Hill, G. J. O. Martin, and H. A. R. Suleria, “Extraction and Characterization of Bioactive Compounds from Diverse Marine Microalgae and Their Potential Antioxidant Activities,” *Chem Biodivers*, vol. 20, no. 11, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1002/cbdv.202300602.
- [46] J. Rumin, R. G. de Oliveira Junior, J. B. Bérard, and L. Picot, “Improving microalgae research and marketing in the european atlantic area: Analysis of major gaps and barriers limiting sector development,” Jun. 01, 2021, *MDPI AG*. doi: 10.3390/md19060319.
- [47] S. Cuellar-Bermudez, I. Aguilar-Hernandez, N. Ornelas-Soto, M. Romero-Ogawa, and R. Parra-Saldivar, “Extraction and purification of high-value metabolites from microalgae: essential lipids, astaxanthin and phycobiliproteins | Enhanced Reader,” *Microb Biotechnol*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 190–209, Sep. 2014, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.12167>.
- [48] A. K. Vuppaladadiyam, P. Prinsen, A. Raheem, R. Luque, and M. Zhao, “Microalgae cultivation and metabolites production: a comprehensive review,” Mar. 01, 2018, *John Wiley and Sons Ltd*. doi: 10.1002/bbb.1864.
- [49] I. Del Pilar, B. Montero, and N. M. Rancel Rodríguez, “POTENCIAL USO BIOTECNOLÓGICO DE POLISACÁRIDOS EXCRETADOS POR MICROALGAS,” 2024.
- [50] M. F. de Souza, E. Meers, and S. Mangini, “The potential of microalgae for carbon capture and sequestration,” *EFB Bioeconomy Journal*, vol. 4, p. 100067, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.bioeco.2024.100067.
- [51] M. Zieliński, M. Dębowski, J. Kazimierowicz, and I. Świca, “Microalgal Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Capture and Utilization from the European Union Perspective,” *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 16, no. 3, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.3390/en16031446.
- [52] J. Zaragoza, “UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA DE NUEVO LEÓN FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS BIOLÓGICAS,” Jul. 2016. Accessed: Nov. 27, 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://eprints.uanl.mx/19627/1/1080314178.pdf>
- [53] S. W. Lestari, A. M. S. Hertika, D. Yona, and N. R. Buwono, “Functional groups in microalgal extracellular polymeric substances: A promising biopolymer for microplastic mitigation in marine ecosystems,” *Ecological Engineering and Environmental Technology*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 159–170, 2025, doi: 10.12912/27197050/199787.
- [54] X. Xiao, W. Li, M. Jin, L. Zhang, L. Qin, and W. Geng, “Responses and tolerance mechanisms of microalgae to heavy metal stress: A review,” Jan. 01, 2023, *Elsevier Ltd*. doi: 10.1016/j.marenvres.2022.105805.
- [55] M. F. De Jesus Raposo, A. M. B. De Morais, and R. M. S. C. De Morais, “Marine polysaccharides from algae with potential biomedical applications,” May 01, 2015, *MDPI AG*. doi: 10.3390/md13052967.
- [56] G. Jiao, G. Yu, J. Zhang, and H. S. Ewart, “Chemical structures and bioactivities of sulfated polysaccharides from marine algae,” *Mar Drugs*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 196–233, 2011, doi: 10.3390/md9020196.
- [57] T. Grande *et al.*, “Chlamydomonas agloeiformis from the Ecuadorian Highlands: Nutrients and Bioactive Compounds Profiling and In Vitro Antioxidant Activity,” *Foods*, vol. 12, no. 17, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.3390/foods12173147.
- [58] P. Trebše, U. Šunta, M. Nenadović, and L. Čizmek, “ALGAE AS A NATURAL RESOURCE OF SKIN PROTECTIVE COMPOUNDS,” 2025.
- [59] R. R. Ambati, P. S. Moi, S. Ravi, and R. G. Aswathanarayana, “Astaxanthin: Sources, extraction, stability, biological activities and its commercial applications - A review,” 2014, *MDPI AG*. doi: 10.3390/md12010128.

- [60] I. Higuera-Ciapara, L. Félix-Valenzuela, and F. M. Goycoolea, “Astaxanthin: A review of its chemistry and applications,” Mar. 2006. doi: 10.1080/10408690590957188.
- [61] E. Ryckebosch, C. Bruneel, K. Muylaert, and I. Foubert, “Microalgae as an alternative source of omega-3 long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids,” *Lipid Technol*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 128–130, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1002/lite.201200197.
- [62] V. Mimouni, L. Ulmann, A. Haimeur, F. Guéno, N. Meskini, and G. Tremblin, “Marine microalgae used as food supplements and their implication in preventing cardiovascular diseases OCL Marine microalgae used as food supplements and their implication in preventing cardiovascular diseases,” vol. 22, no. 4, 2015, doi: 10.1051/ocl/2015015i.
- [63] T. A. Conde *et al.*, “Microalgal lipid extracts have potential to modulate the inflammatory response: A critical review,” Sep. 01, 2021, *MDPI*. doi: 10.3390/ijms22189825.
- [64] M. Tabarzad, V. Atabaki, and T. Hosseinabadi, “Anti-inflammatory Activity of Bioactive Compounds from Microalgae and Cyanobacteria by Focusing on the Mechanisms of Action,” Aug. 01, 2020, *Springer Science+Business Media B.V.* doi: 10.1007/s11033-020-05562-9.
- [65] M. Dimopoulou, A. Kolonas, D. Stagos, and O. Gortzi, “A Review of the Sustainability, Chemical Composition, Bioactive Compounds, Antioxidant and Antidiabetic Activity, Neuroprotective Properties, and Health Benefits of Microalgae,” Mar. 01, 2025, *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)*. doi: 10.3390/biomass5010011.
- [66] J. Cichoński and G. Chrzanowski, “Microalgae as a Source of Valuable Phenolic Compounds and Carotenoids,” Dec. 01, 2022, *MDPI*. doi: 10.3390/molecules27248852.
- [67] M. C. Guamán-Burneo, N. González-Romero, A. Santillán-Sarmiento, M. C. Guamán-Burneo, N. González-Romero, and A. Santillán-Sarmiento, “Microalgal Diversity in the Ecuadorian Tropical Andes and Its Association with Abiotic Factors,” *Hydrobiology 2025, Vol. 4*, vol. 4, no. 4, p. 28, Oct. 2025, doi: 10.3390/HYDROBIOLOGY4040028.
- [68] S. Méndez-Ancca *et al.*, “Physicochemical Evaluation of Cushuro (*Nostoc sphaericum* Vaucher ex Bornet & Flahault) in the Region of Moquegua for Food Purposes,” *Foods 2023, Vol. 12*, vol. 12, no. 10, May 2023, doi: 10.3390/FOODS12101939.
- [69] A. Sarwer *et al.*, “Algal biomass valorization for biofuel production and carbon sequestration: a review,” *Environmental Chemistry Letters 2022 20:5*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 2797–2851, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1007/S10311-022-01458-1.
- [70] C. Lloyd *et al.*, “Identification of microalgae cultured in Bold’s Basal medium from freshwater samples, from a high-rise city,” *Scientific Reports 2021 11:1*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 4474-, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-84112-0.
- [71] N. Coulombier, T. Jauffrais, and N. Lebouvier, “Antioxidant compounds from microalgae: A review,” *Mar Drugs*, vol. 19, no. 10, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/MD19100549/S1.
- [72] D. Ronga *et al.*, “Microalgal Biostimulants and Biofertilisers in Crop Productions,” *Agronomy 2019, Vol. 9*, vol. 9, no. 4, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.3390/AGRONOMY9040192.
- [73] A. S. Bello, I. Saadaoui, R. Ben-Hamadou, A. S. Bello, I. Saadaoui, and R. Ben-Hamadou, “‘Beyond the Source of Bioenergy’: Microalgae in Modern Agriculture as a Biostimulant, Biofertilizer, and Anti-Abiotic Stress,” *Agronomy 2021, Vol. 11*, vol. 11, no. 8, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.3390/AGRONOMY11081610.
- [74] M. Martínez-Ruiz *et al.*, “Microalgae Bioactive Compounds to Topical Applications Products—A Review,” *Molecules 2022, Vol. 27*, vol. 27, no. 11, May 2022, doi: 10.3390/MOLECULES27113512.
- [75] H. J. Y. Leong, M. L. Teoh, J. Beardall, and P. Convey, “Green beauty unveiled: Exploring the potential of microalgae for skin whitening, photoprotection and anti-aging applications in cosmetics,” *Journal of Applied Phycology 2024 36:6*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 3315–3328, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1007/S10811-024-03345-4.

- [76] J. C. A. Braun and L. M. Colla, "Use of Microalgae for the Development of Biofertilizers and Biostimulants," *BioEnergy Research* 2022 16:1, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 289–310, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1007/S12155-022-10456-8.
- [77] P. Parmar, R. Kumar, Y. Neha, and V. Srivatsan, "Microalgae as next generation plant growth additives: Functions, applications, challenges and circular bioeconomy based solutions," 2023, *Frontiers Media S.A.* doi: 10.3389/fpls.2023.1073546.
- [78] T. Chen *et al.*, "Manganese Ferrite Nanoparticle-Assisted Enhancement of Photosynthetic Carbon Sequestration in Microalgae," *Sustainability* 2025, Vol. 17, vol. 17, no. 10, May 2025, doi: 10.3390/SU17104303.
- [79] H. Dahai *et al.*, "The application of magical microalgae in carbon sequestration and emission reduction: Removal mechanisms and potential analysis," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 197, p. 114417, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.RSER.2024.114417.
- [80] X. Xu, X. Gu, Z. Wang, W. Shatner, and Z. Wang, "Progress, challenges and solutions of research on photosynthetic carbon sequestration efficiency of microalgae," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 110, pp. 65–82, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.RSER.2019.04.050.
- [81] V. Rosaldo-Benitez, G. A. Ayil-Chan, N. Labrín-Sotomayor, R. Valdéz-Ojeda, and Y. J. Peña-Ramírez, "Eukaryotic Microalgae Communities from Tropical Karstic Freshwater Lagoons in an Anthropogenic Disturbance Gradient Microscopic and Metagenomic Analysis," *Microorganisms*, vol. 12, no. 11, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.3390/MICROORGANISMS12112368/S1.
- [82] S. R. Chia *et al.*, "Sustainable approaches for algae utilisation in bioenergy production," *Renew Energy*, vol. 129, pp. 838–852, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.RENENE.2017.04.001.
- [83] S. K. Saha, P. Murray, S. K. Saha, and P. Murray, "Exploitation of Microalgae Species for Nutraceutical Purposes: Cultivation Aspects," *Fermentation* 2018, Vol. 4, vol. 4, no. 2, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.3390/FERMENTATION4020046.
- [84] W. Mulbry, E. K. Westhead, C. Pizarro, and L. Sikora, "Recycling of manure nutrients: use of algal biomass from dairy manure treatment as a slow release fertilizer," *Bioresour Technol*, vol. 96, no. 4, pp. 451–458, Mar. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2004.05.026.
- [85] I. Rawat, R. Ranjith Kumar, T. Mutanda, and F. Bux, "Dual role of microalgae: Phycoremediation of domestic wastewater and biomass production for sustainable biofuels production," *Appl Energy*, vol. 88, no. 10, pp. 3411–3424, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.11.025.
- [86] A. G. Olabi *et al.*, "Emerging Technologies for Enhancing Microalgae Biofuel Production: Recent Progress, Barriers, and Limitations," *Fermentation*, vol. 8, no. 11, p. 649, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.3390/fermentation8110649.
- [87] N. K. Sarker and P. Kaparaju, "Microalgal Bioeconomy: A Green Economy Approach Towards Achieving Sustainable Development Goals," *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 24, p. 11218, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.3390/su162411218.
- [88] P. M. Slegers, P. J. M. van Beveren, R. H. Wijffels, G. Van Straten, and A. J. B. Van Boxtel, "Scenario analysis of large scale algae production in tubular photobioreactors," *Appl Energy*, vol. 105, pp. 395–406, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.12.068.
- [89] P. Erbland, S. Caron, M. Peterson, and A. Alyokhin, "Design and performance of a low-cost, automated, large-scale photobioreactor for microalgae production," *Aquac Eng*, vol. 90, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.aquaeng.2020.102103.
- [90] "Cultivos a cielo abierto de las cianobacterias Nostoc LAUN0015 y Anabaena MOF015 para la producción de biomasa enriquecida. Pruebas piloto para cultivos masivos".

-
- [91] L. Guillermo, R. Mérida, L. Queiroz Zepka, and E. Jacob-Lopes, “FOTOBIORREACTOR: HERRAMIENTA PARA CULTIVO DE CIANOBACTERIAS PHOTOBIOREACTOR: TOOL FOR MASS CULTIVATION OF CYANOBACTERIA.” [Online]. Available: <http://spirulina.greennutritionals>.
- [92] F. Deimar, “INFLUENCE OF THE PARAMETERS PHYSICOCHEMICAL ON THE OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF THE WATERS OF THE RESERVOIR SAN JACINTO,” 2018.
- [93] P. Pushpangadan, V. George, T. Parambil Ijinu, and M. Ambika Chithra, “Biodiversity, Bioprospecting, Traditional Knowledge, Sustainable Development and Value Added Products: A Review,” *J Tradit Med Clin Naturop*, vol. 07, no. 01, 2018, doi: 10.4172/2573-4555.1000256.
- [94] C. B. Barrett and T. J. Lybbert, “Is bioprospecting a viable strategy for conserving tropical ecosystems?,” *Ecological Economics*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 293–300, Sep. 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0921-8009(00)00188-9.
- [95] C. Brugère, J. Aguilar-Manjarrez, M. C. M. Beveridge, and D. Soto, “The ecosystem approach to aquaculture 10 years on – a critical review and consideration of its future role in blue growth,” *Rev Aquac*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 493–514, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1111/raq.12242.
- [96] W. M. Guerrero-Villegas, M. C. Gallegos-Varela, P. M. Rosero-Rosero, and L. M. Pinargote-Yépez, “Economía circular en contextos locales: caso Ecuador,” *Revista Direito GV*, vol. 20, 2024, doi: 10.1590/2317-6172202430.